

Novel Neutron Noise Unfolding Methods and Applications for Anomaly Detection in 2D HTTR Core

Harun Ardiansyah^{1,*}, Tomasz Kozlowski¹

¹Department of Nuclear, Plasma, and Radiological Engineering, The Grainger College of Engineering, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, Urbana, Illinois, USA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803920

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces new neutron noise unfolding method based on Green's function called the greedy method. Neutron noise unfolding methods are the methods used to determine the magnitude, location, energy, and frequency of neutron noise sources. The challenge of neutron noise unfolding is that neutron noise is not known at all positions and neutron energy. It is only known at the detector positions. The greedy method iterates Green's function to find the Green's function matrix and the local minimum of the residual. This results in several valid solutions to the noise sources. The correct solution is the one that requires the least number of Green's function combinations to minimize the residual. The method is compared with the scanning method, which is the standard method. The scanning method minimizes the ratio of neutron noise and the Green's function at two different detector locations. This is done iteratively for all combinations of two detectors. Both methods are applied to unfold noise sources in 2D HTTR core. The noise sources are defined as absorber of variable strength (AVS) type noise sources. The results indicate that the scanning method shows satisfactory results but is limited to only one AVS-type source. For the greedy method, the results show that the greedy method is able to unfold multiple neutron noise sources simultaneously.

Keywords: neutron noise, unfolding methods, scanning, greedy method

1. INTRODUCTION

Neutron noise unfolding methods are methods that are used to determine the parameters of neutron noise sources, including their magnitude, frequency, energy, and location. There have been many efforts to develop neutron noise unfolding methods. These methods include the inversion method, zoning method, scanning method [1], and methods based on machine learning [2]. These methods have been applied to the AVS-type noise sources in reactor cores [1], [3]. The three methods mentioned earlier (inversion, zoning, and scanning) rely on the use of Green's function, which can be generated as a database without the need to know the true neutron noise source in the core. The Green's function can be derived from the neutron noise equation. In operator form, Equation (1) defines the linearized neutron noise equation in frequency domain.

$$B(\mathbf{r}, \omega)\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = S(\mathbf{r}, \omega) \quad (1)$$

where $B(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$ is the Boltzmann-like operator for the complex neutron noise equation and $S(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$ is the neutron noise source term. Since neutron noise source can be described as a localized (impulse-like) perturbation, we can use Green's function to describe the impulse [4].

$$B(\mathbf{r}, \omega)G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega) = \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_p) \quad (2)$$

*haruna2@illinois.edu

where \mathbf{r} is a given location and \mathbf{r}_p is the location of the noise source. In order to compute the Green's function $G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega)$, Equation (2) is solved for some chosen set of deltas (e.g. the spatial mesh of the core). Then, we can define,

$$\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = \int_{\mathbf{r}_p} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega) S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega) d\mathbf{r}_p \quad (3)$$

where,

$\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$ = Neutron noise

$G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega)$ = Green's function matrix

$S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega)$ = Neutron noise source to be unfolded

In matrix form, Equation (3) can be written as matrix-vector multiplication:

$$\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega) D(\mathbf{r}_p) S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega) \quad (4)$$

where $\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$ has size $(GN \times 1)$, $G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega)$ has sized $(GN \times GN)$, $D(\mathbf{r}_p)$ is the diagonal matrix with size $(GN \times GN)$ containing the mesh area/volume, and $S(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$ has size $(GN \times 1)$. G is the number of energy groups, and N is the number of spatial mesh. Therefore, the noise source can be determined by inverting the Green's function such that:

$$S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega) = \left(G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega) D(\mathbf{r}_p) \right)^{-1} \delta\phi(\mathbf{r}, \omega) \quad (5)$$

Suppose the neutron noise is known at every location in the core. In that case, it is trivial to unfold the neutron noise sources by inverting the Green's function matrix. However, this is not the case due to the limitation of detector locations. This means that Equation (5) should be written as:

$$S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega) = \left(G(\mathbf{r}_{meas}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega) D(\mathbf{r}_p) \right)^{-1} (\mathbf{r}_{meas}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega) \delta\phi(\mathbf{r}_{meas}, \omega) \quad (6)$$

Where $\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}_{meas}, \omega)$ means that the neutron noise is known at detector locations (measured) and zero otherwise. This creates a non-square matrix for the Green's function, which makes it ill-posed to invert. This is the main challenge of neutron noise unfolding methods.

This paper introduces a novel neutron noise unfolding method based on Green's function, called the greedy method. This method is compared with the scanning method for 2D HTTR core application. The structure of this paper is as follows. First, we will introduce the greedy method as the new neutron noise unfolding method. Second, we outline the derivation of the scanning method. Finally, we apply both methods to the 2D HTTR core and show some results for multiple AVS-type noise sources.

2. NEUTRON NOISE UNFOLDING METHODS

2.1. Greedy Method

Considering the limitations of the existing methods (i.e. inversion, zoning, and scanning) [1], improvement of neutron noise unfolding method to be able to unfold multiple noise sources at once. In this paper, we introduce a novel method utilizing Green's function. For a finite mesh, we can discretize Equation (3) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\phi(\mathbf{r}, \omega) &= \int_{\mathbf{r}_p} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega) S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega) d\mathbf{r}_p \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{r}_p} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega) S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega) \Delta\mathbf{r}_p \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\Delta\mathbf{r}_p$ is the area/volume of the mesh. Since the $G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega)$ and $\Delta\mathbf{r}_p$ are given, then the neutron noise $\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$ is the sum of combination of Green's function with coefficient $S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega)$. The system of

equations in Equation (7) is an underconstrained system of linear equations since the neutron noise is only known at the detectors' positions. Methods from other fields have been used to solve this system of equations. One of the fields that has similar problem is compressed sensing [5]. In compressed sensing, the system of linear equations is constructed based on the summation of a weighted set of basis functions. These sets of basis functions are then used to match the set of measurements [6]. In reactor physics, this method has been applied in various contexts, including neutron flux distribution [7] and temperature distribution construction [6].

In this paper, we introduce a method inspired by greedy algorithms, such as matching pursuit [8], for neutron noise reconstruction. In a matching pursuit, the basis function used for the construction is orthonormal [8]. Meanwhile, the basis function in our case is Green's function, which is not orthonormal. Therefore, a different approach is needed to utilize Green's function as the basis function. The goal of the greedy method is to find a polynomial combination of Green's function that solves Equation (7). It can be written as follows:

$$\min \|G(\mathbf{r}, \omega)\|_0 \quad \text{subject to} \quad \delta\phi = G(\mathbf{r})S \quad (8)$$

After the reconstructed neutron noise is done, solving for $S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega)$ is trivial.

The general idea of the greedy method is to append a column of Green's function matrix $G(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$ in every iteration until the appended selection reaches the lowest residual norm. The input of this method is the measured neutron noise, calculated Green's function, and mesh information. The measured neutron noise is obtained from the reference neutron noise calculation, but only nonzero at the detector locations. It is assumed that the detector itself does not produce any noise that could interfere with the neutron noise.

There are two iterations in the greedy method, the inner and outer iterations. The inner iterations start from a single column i , then we define the initial residual norm from the measured neutron noise in Equation (9).

$$r_i^0 = \|\delta\phi_{meas}\|_2 \quad (9)$$

At each step of the inner iteration, all columns of the Green's function $j \neq i$ are examined. Each candidate column j is temporarily appended to the current selection j^* (which initially contains column i), and the corresponding coefficients S are computed using the Least Square method. Then, the residual norm for that iteration is computed using Equation (10). The columns j^* that yield the smallest residual norm is then selected as the next column to include. This selection can be written as follows:

$$\varepsilon(j) = \min_{G_j} \|G(j, \mathbf{r}, \omega)S - \delta\phi_{meas}\|_2 \quad (10)$$

The selected columns j^* is then carried over to the next inner iteration. The inner iteration is performed until the desired residual norm is reached. This is then saved as a list of valid solutions. After that, the outer iteration continues to pick the next column as a starting point of inner iteration. The output of the outer iteration is a list of valid Green's function solutions with length ($group \times N$). From these valid solutions, the solution that has the least number of Green's function columns is selected as the correct solution for the neutron noise reconstruction.

The flow diagram of the method is seen in Figure 1.

2.2. Scanning Method

The scanning method compares the neutron noise detected by the detector with the calculated response for all possible locations of the noise source within the system. The noise source is accurately identified when the calculated neutron noise matches the measured neutron noise [1]. This method was developed by [3] and extended by [9]. Both investigations successfully determined the location of the unseated fuel assembly in the Swedish Forsmark-1 BWR. Both use Green's function as the means to compare detector readings.

This method starts with the definition of neutron noise at a given location \mathbf{r} induced by a noise source located at the location \mathbf{r}_p as follows:

$$\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega) D(\mathbf{r}_p) S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega) \quad (11)$$

Using Equation (11) to compare with the detector reading is difficult since the location and strength of the noise are unknown. If one has access to two detectors at locations A and B, the ratio between the neutron noise at these two locations can be used to eliminate the noise source strength:

$$\frac{\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}_A, \omega)}{\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}_B, \omega)} = \frac{G(\mathbf{r}_A, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega)}{G(\mathbf{r}_B, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega)} \quad (12)$$

Figure 1. Flow diagram of greedy method

Then, the scanning algorithm consists of minimizing the following:

$$\Delta(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{A,B} \left| \frac{\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}_A, \omega)}{\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}_B, \omega)} - \frac{G(\mathbf{r}_A, \mathbf{r}, \omega)}{G(\mathbf{r}_B, \mathbf{r}, \omega)} \right| \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) implied that the summation is done for all the detector pairs of all locations \mathbf{r} . If there exist n number of detectors in the reactor, the number of detector pairs is as follows:

$$N_{\text{detector pair}} = \frac{n \times (n + 1)}{2} \quad (14)$$

The location at which the minimum value of $\Delta(\mathbf{r})$ is found indicates the location of the noise source. The magnitude of the noise source can be calculated as follows:

$$S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega) = \frac{\delta\phi(\mathbf{r}_m, \omega)}{G(\mathbf{r}_m, \mathbf{r}_p, \omega)} \quad (15)$$

For any detector m .

3. OVERVIEW OF 2D HTTR

The HTTR is a high-temperature gas-cooled prismatic-block reactor built by the JAEA (Japan Atomic Energy Agency) [10]. It is a graphite-moderated and helium gas-cooled reactor. The construction of HTTR started in 1991 at the JAEA O-arai Research and Development Center. The first criticality was achieved in 1998, and full operation began in 2001 [10].

HTTR is an annular core, which consists of fuel blocks, control rod blocks, replaceable reflectors, and irradiation blocks. Permanent reflectors surround the core. HTTR utilizes TRISO fuel particles, which are incorporated into the fuel pellets. The fuel pellets are stacked in the fuel pins, and the fuel pins are placed in the fuel block, as seen in Figure 2 [11]. The fuel of HTTR is UO_2 with different levels of enrichment depending on the location of the block. The fuel enrichment in HTTR ranges from 3.4% to 9.9% of U-235. This paper uses HTTR startup core at cold zero-power conditions as the reference case. The 2D case is taken from the mid-plane block of the 3D case. The full details of the HTTR startup core is available in [10], [11].

Figure 2. Configuration map for 2D HTTR case

4. NEUTRON NOISE UNFOLDING FOR 2D HTTR

4.1. Single Mesh AVS-type Source

In this simulation, a single AVS source is unfolded using both the scanning and greedy methods. The results of the neutron noise source $S(\mathbf{r}_p, \omega)$ are compared with the reference solution calculated for the scenario. The simulation is done with a constant frequency of 1 Hz.

Figure 3 shows the location of the AVS source and detectors. The result of the simulation is described in Table I.

Figure 3. Location of source and detectors in the 2D HTTR for single noise source case

Table I. Single noise source in 2D HTTR

Method	Energy Group	Hex Number	Neutron Noise Source (n/cm^3)	Match?
Reference	1	14	$-4.893 \times 10^{-5} + 0.000i$	--
Scanning	1	14	$-4.893 \times 10^{-5} + 0.000i$	Yes
Greedy	1	14	$-4.893 \times 10^{-5} + 0.000i$	Yes

The results show that both scanning and greedy methods manage to unfold the neutron noise source. This is an expected behavior. For the scanning method, it works well for a single mesh source since it minimizes the difference between the neutron noise ratio and Green's function ratio. The minimum difference is located in the noise source location. For the greedy method, the method works well to exactly match the references.

4.2. Two Mesh AVS-type Source

In this simulation, a two-mesh AVS source is unfolded using both the existing and novel methods. The simulation is done with a constant frequency of 0.056 Hz. Figure 4 shows the location of the AVS source and detectors. The result of the simulation is described in Table II.

Figure 4. Location of source and detectors in the 2D HTTR for two noise sources case

Table II. Two noise sources in 2D HTTR

Method	Energy Group	Hex Number	Neutron Noise Source (n/cm^3)	Match?
Reference	1	48	$-1.882 \times 10^{-3} + 0.000i$	--
	2	60	$-5.189 \times 10^{-3} - 4.670 \times 10^{-3}i$	--
Scanning	2	60	$-1.033 \times 10^{-2} - 4.138 \times 10^{-3}i$	No
	1	1	$0.000 + 0.000i$	No
Greedy	1	48	$-1.882 \times 10^{-3} + 0.000i$	Yes
	2	60	$-5.189 \times 10^{-3} - 4.670 \times 10^{-3}i$	Yes

The results show that the scanning method fails to unfold the neutron noise source. The scanning method fails due to the method's limitation, as it only points to one location which minimizes Equation (13). On the other hand, greedy method manages to unfold the neutron noise source. This is expected behavior for both methods.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces a new neutron noise unfolding method, namely the greedy method. This method is developed based on the matching pursuit algorithm that has been used in compressed sensing. The method is applied to a 2D HTTR core and compared with the scanning method. In this paper, the neutron noise sources are AVS-type noise sources. The results show that the scanning method only works for single mesh noise source. On the other hand, the results for the greedy method show that it is capable of unfolding multiple neutron noise sources simultaneously. Future work is needed to assess the limits of the greedy method for multiple noise sources, as well as application of greedy method to vibration noise sources.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Demazière and G. Andhill, "Identification and localization of absorbers of variable strength in nuclear reactors," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 32, no. 8, pp. 812–842, May 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2004.12.011.

- [2] S. A. Hosseini and I. E. P. Afrakoti, “On a various soft computing algorithms for reconstruction of the neutron noise source in the nuclear reactor cores,” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 114, pp. 19–31, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2017.12.015.
- [3] J. K.-H. Karlsson and I. Pázsit, “Localization of a Channel Instability in the Forsmark-1 Boiling Water Reactor,” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 26, pp. 1183–1204, 1999, doi: 10.1016/S0306-4549(99)00014-6.
- [4] I. Pázsit, “Investigation of the Space-Dependent Noise Induced by A Vibrating Absorber,” *Atomkernenergie*, Jan. 1977.
- [5] D. L. Donoho, “Compressed sensing,” *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 1289–1306, Apr. 2006, doi: 10.1109/TIT.2006.871582.
- [6] D. Price, M. I. Radaideh, and B. Kochunas, “Simplified matching pursuits applied to 3D nuclear reactor temperature distribution construction,” *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 131, pp. 134–158, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.apm.2024.04.011.
- [7] S. K. Bahuguna, S. Mukhopadhyay, and A. P. Tiwari, “Signal recovery from sparse measurements by using compressed sensing techniques for reactor core flux mapping,” in *2017 International Conference on Wireless Communications, Signal Processing and Networking (WiSPNET)*, Mar. 2017, pp. 206–212. doi: 10.1109/WiSPNET.2017.8299749.
- [8] S. G. Mallat and Z. Zhang, “Matching pursuits with time-frequency dictionaries,” *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 41, no. 12, pp. 3397–3415, Dec. 1993, doi: 10.1109/78.258082.
- [9] C. Demazière, “Development of a noise-based method for the determination of the moderator temperature coefficient of reactivity (MTC) in pressurized water reactors (PWRs),” Chalmers Univ. of Technology, Göteborg, 2002.
- [10] M. Goto, N. Nojiri, and S. Shimakawa, “Neutronics Calculations of HTTR with Several Nuclear Data Libraries,” *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, vol. 43, no. 10, pp. 1237–1244, Oct. 2006, doi: 10.1080/18811248.2006.9711217.
- [11] J. D. Bess and N. Fujimoto, “Benchmark Evaluation of Start-Up and Zero-Power Measurements at the High-Temperature Engineering Test Reactor,” *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, vol. 178, no. 3, pp. 414–427, Nov. 2014, doi: 10.13182/NSE14-14.